

Smarandache Idempotents in finite ring Z_n and in Group Ring $Z_n G$

W.B.Vasantha and Moon K.Chetry

Department of Mathematics
I.I.T. Madras, Chennai

Abstract In this paper we analyze and study the Smarandache idempotents (S-idempotents) in the ring Z_n and in the group ring $Z_n G$ of a finite group G over the finite ring Z_n . We have shown the existence of Smarandache idempotents (S-idempotents) in the ring Z_n when $n = 2^m p$ (or $3p$), where p is a prime > 2 (or p a prime > 3). Also we have shown the existence of Smarandache idempotents (S-idempotents) in the group ring $Z_2 G$ and $Z_2 S_n$ where $n = 2^m p$ (p a prime of the form $2^m t + 1$).

§1. Introduction

This paper has 4 sections. In section 1, we just give the basic definition of S-idempotents in rings. In section 2, we prove the existence of S-idempotents in the ring Z_n where $n = 2^m p$, $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and p is an odd prime. We also prove the existence of S-idempotents for the ring Z_n where n is of the form $n = 3p$, p is a prime greater than 3. In section 3, we prove the existence of S-idempotents in group rings $Z_2 G$ of cyclic group G over Z_2 where order of G is n , $n = 2^m p$ (p a prime of the form $2^m t + 1$). We also prove the existence of S-idempotents for the group ring $Z_2 S_n$ where $n = 2^m p$ (p a prime of the form $2^m t + 1$). In the final section, we propose some interesting number theoretic problems based on our study.

Here we just recollect the definition of Smarandache idempotents (S-idempotent) and some basic results to make this paper a self contained one.

Definition 1.1[5]. Let R be a ring. An element $x \in R$ is said to be a Smarandache idempotent (S-idempotent) of R if $x^2 = x$ and there exist $a \in R$, $a \neq 0$ such that

$$i. \quad a^2 = x$$

$$ii. \quad xa = x \quad \text{or} \quad ax = a.$$

Example 1.1. Let $Z_{10} = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 9\}$ be the ring of integers modulo 10. Here

$$6^2 \equiv 6 \pmod{10}, \quad 4^2 \equiv 6 \pmod{10}$$

and

$$6 \cdot 4 \equiv 4 \pmod{10}.$$

So 6 is a S-idempotent in Z_{10} .

Example 1.2. Take $Z_{12} = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 11\}$ the ring of integers modulo 12. Here

$$4^2 \equiv 4(\text{mod}12), \quad 8^2 \equiv 4(\text{mod}12)$$

and

$$4 \cdot 8 \equiv 8(\text{mod}12).$$

So 4 is a S-idempotent in Z_{12} .

Example 1.3. In $Z_{30} = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 29\}$ the ring of integers modulo 30, 25 is a S-idempotent. As

$$25^2 \equiv 25(\text{mod}30), \quad 5^2 \equiv 25(\text{mod}30)$$

and

$$25 \cdot 5 \equiv 5(\text{mod}30).$$

So 25 is a S-idempotent in Z_{30} .

Theorem 1.1 [5]. *Let R be a ring. If $x \in R$ is a S-idempotent then it is an idempotent in R .*

Proof. From the very definition of S-idempotents.

§2. S-idempotents in the finite ring Z_n

In this section, we find conditions for Z_n to have S-idempotents and prove that when n is of the form $2^m p$, p a prime ≥ 2 or $n = 3p$ (p a prime ≥ 3) has S-idempotents. We also explicitly find all the S-idempotents.

Theorem 2.1. $Z_p = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, p-1\}$, the prime field of characteristic p , where p is a prime has no non-trivial S-idempotents.

Proof. Straightforward, as every S-idempotents are idempotents and Z_p has no non-trivial idempotents.

Theorem 2.2: *The ring Z_{2p} , where p is an odd prime has S-idempotents.*

Proof. Here p is an odd prime, so p must be of the form $2m + 1$ i.e $p = 2m + 1$. Take

$$x = p + 1 \quad \text{and} \quad a = p - 1.$$

Here

$$\begin{aligned} p^2 = (2m + 1)^2 &= 4m^2 + 4m + 1 \\ &= 2m(2m + 1) + 2m + 1 \\ &= 2pm + p \\ &\equiv p(\text{mod}2p). \end{aligned}$$

So

$$p^2 \equiv p(\text{mod}2p).$$

Again

$$\begin{aligned}x^2 &= (p+1)^2 \equiv p^2 + 1 \pmod{2p} \\ &\equiv p + 1 \pmod{2p}.\end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$x^2 = x.$$

Also

$$a^2 = (p-1)^2 \equiv p + 1 \pmod{2p},$$

therefore

$$a^2 = x.$$

And

$$\begin{aligned}xa &= (p+1)(p-1) \\ &= p^2 - 1 \\ &\equiv p - 1 \pmod{2p}\end{aligned}$$

therefore

$$xa = a.$$

So $x = p + 1$ is a S-idempotent in Z_{2p} .

Example 2.1. Take $Z_6 = Z_{2 \cdot 3} = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ the ring of integers modulo 6. Then $x = 3 + 1 = 4$ is a S-idempotent. As

$$x^2 = 4^2 \equiv 4 \pmod{6},$$

take $a = 2$, then $a^2 = 2^2 \equiv 4 \pmod{6}$.

Therefore

$$a^2 = x,$$

and

$$xa = 4 \cdot 2 \equiv 2 \pmod{6}$$

i.e

$$xa = a.$$

Theorem 2.3. *The ring Z_{2^2p} , p a prime > 2 and is of the form $4m + 1$ or $4m + 3$ has (at least) two S-idempotents.*

Proof. Here p is of the form $4m + 1$ or $4m + 3$.

If $p = 4m + 1$, then $p^2 \equiv p \pmod{2^2p}$. As

$$\begin{aligned}p^2 &= (4m+1)^2 \\ &= 16m^2 + 8m + 1 \\ &= 4m(4m+1) + 4m + 1 \\ &= 4pm + p \\ &\equiv p \pmod{2^2p},\end{aligned}$$

therefore

$$p^2 \equiv p \pmod{2^2 p}.$$

Now, take $x = 3p + 1$ and $a = p - 1$ then

$$\begin{aligned} x^2 = (3p + 1)^2 &= 9p^2 + 6p + 1 \\ &\equiv 9p + 6p + 1 \pmod{2^2 p} \\ &\equiv 3p + 1 \pmod{2^2 p} \end{aligned}$$

therefore

$$a^2 = x.$$

And

$$\begin{aligned} xa &= (3p + 1)(p - 1) \\ &= 3p^2 - 3p + p - 1 \\ &\equiv p - 1 \pmod{2^2 p} \end{aligned}$$

therefore

$$xa = a.$$

So x is an S-idempotent.

Similarly, we can prove that $y = p$, (here take $a = 3p$) is another S-idempotent. These are the only two S-idempotents in $Z_{2^2 p}$ when $p = 4m + 1$. If $p = 4m + 3$, then $p^2 \equiv 3p \pmod{2^2 p}$.

As above, we can show that $x = p + 1$, ($a = 3p - 1$) and $y = 3p$, ($a = p$) are the two S-idempotents. So we are getting a nice pattern here for S-idempotents in $Z_{2^2 p}$:

I. If $p = 4m + 1$, then $x = 3p + 1$, ($a = p - 1$) and $y = p$, ($a = 3p$) are the two S-idempotents.

II. If $p = 4m + 3$, $x = p + 1$, ($a = 3p - 1$) and $y = 3p$, ($a = p$) are the two S-idempotents.

Example 2.2. Take $Z_{2^2 \cdot 5} = \{0, 1, \dots, 19\}$, here $5 = 4 \cdot 1 + 1$. So $x = 3 \cdot 5 + 1 = 16$, ($a = 5 - 1 = 4$) is an S-idempotent. As $16^2 \equiv 16 \pmod{20}$, $4^2 \equiv 16 \pmod{20}$ and $16 \cdot 4 \equiv 4 \pmod{20}$. Also $y = 5$, ($a = 3 \cdot 5 = 15$) is another S-idempotent. As $5^2 \equiv 5 \pmod{20}$, $15^2 \equiv 5 \pmod{20}$ and $5 \cdot 15 \equiv 15 \pmod{20}$.

Example 2.3. In the ring $Z_{2^2 \cdot 7} = \{0, 1, \dots, 27\}$, here $7 = 4 \cdot 1 + 3$, $x = 7 + 1 = 8$, ($a = 3 \cdot 7 - 1 = 20$) is an S-idempotent. As $8^2 \equiv 8 \pmod{28}$, $20^2 \equiv 8 \pmod{28}$ and $8 \cdot 20 \equiv 20 \pmod{28}$. Also $y = 3 \cdot 7 = 21$, ($a = 7$) is another S-idempotent. As $21^2 \equiv 21 \pmod{28}$, $7^2 \equiv 21 \pmod{28}$ and $21 \cdot 7 \equiv 7 \pmod{28}$.

Theorem 2.4. The ring $Z_{2^3 p}$, p a prime > 2 has (at least) two S-idempotents of $\phi(2^3)$ types (where $\phi(n)$ is the number of integer less than n and relatively prime to n).

Proof. As p is prime > 2 . So p is one of the $8m + 1, 8m + 3, 8m + 5, 8m + 7$. Now we will get the following two S-idempotents for each $\phi(2^3) = 4$ types of prime p .

I. If $p = 8m + 1$, then $x = 7p + 1$, ($a = p - 1$) and $y = p$, ($a = 7p$) are S-idempotents.

II. If $p = 8m + 3$, then $x = 5p + 1$, ($a = 3p - 1$) and $y = 3p$, ($a = 5p$) are S-idempotents.

III. If $p = 8m + 5$, then $x = 3p + 1$, ($a = 5p - 1$) and $y = 5p$, ($a = 3p$) are S-idempotents.

IV. If $p = 8m + 7$, then $x = p + 1$, ($a = 7p - 1$) and $y = 7p$, ($a = p$) are S-idempotents.

Example 2.4. In the ring $Z_{2^3 \cdot 3} = \{0, 1, \dots, 23\}$, here $3 = 8 \cdot 0 + 3$. So $x = 5 \cdot 3 + 1 = 16$, ($a = 3 \cdot 3 - 1 = 8$) is an S-idempotent. As $16^2 \equiv 16 \pmod{24}$, $8^2 \equiv 16 \pmod{24}$ and $16 \cdot 8 \equiv 8 \pmod{24}$. Also $y = 3 \cdot 3 = 9$, ($a = 5 \cdot 3 = 15$) is another S-idempotent. As $9^2 \equiv 9 \pmod{24}$, $15^2 \equiv 9 \pmod{24}$ and $9 \cdot 15 \equiv 15 \pmod{24}$.

Example 2.5. Take $Z_{2^3 \cdot 13} = Z_{104} = \{0, 1, \dots, 103\}$, here $13 = 8 \cdot 1 + 5$. So $x = 3 \cdot 13 + 1 = 40$, ($a = 5 \cdot 13 - 1 = 64$) is an S-idempotent. As $40^2 \equiv 40 \pmod{104}$, $64^2 \equiv 40 \pmod{104}$ and $40 \cdot 64 \equiv 64 \pmod{104}$. Also $y = 5 \cdot 13 = 65$, ($a = 3 \cdot 13 = 39$) is another S-idempotent. As $65^2 \equiv 65 \pmod{104}$, $39^2 \equiv 65 \pmod{104}$ and $65 \cdot 39 \equiv 39 \pmod{104}$.

Theorem 2.5. *The ring $Z_{2^4 p}$, p a prime > 2 has (at least) two S-idempotents for each of $\phi(2^4)$ types of prime p .*

Proof. As above, we can list the S-idempotents for all $\phi(2^4) = 8$ types of prime p .

I. If $p = 16m + 1$, then $x = 15p + 1$, ($a = p - 1$) and $y = p$, ($a = 15p$) are S-idempotents.

II. If $p = 16m + 3$, then $x = 13p + 1$, ($a = 3p - 1$) and $y = 3p$, ($a = 13p$) are S-idempotents.

III. If $p = 16m + 5$, then $x = 11p + 1$, ($a = 5p - 1$) and $y = 5p$, ($a = 11p$) are S-idempotents.

IV. If $p = 16m + 7$, then $x = 9p + 1$, ($a = 7p - 1$) and $y = 7p$, ($a = 9p$) are S-idempotents.

V. If $p = 16m + 9$, then $x = 7p + 1$, ($a = 9p - 1$) and $y = 9p$, ($a = 7p$) are S-idempotents.

VI. If $p = 16m + 11$, then $x = 5p + 1$, ($a = 11p - 1$) and $y = 11p$, ($a = 5p$) are S-idempotents.

VII. If $p = 16m + 13$, then $x = 3p + 1$, ($a = 13p - 1$) and $y = 13p$, ($a = 13p$) are S-idempotents.

VIII. If $p = 16m + 15$, then $x = p + 1$, ($a = 15p - 1$) and $y = 15p$, ($a = p$) are S-idempotents.

Example 2.6. In the ring $Z_{2^4 \cdot 17} = Z_{272} = \{0, 1, \dots, 271\}$, here $17 = 16 \cdot 1 + 1$. So $x = 15 \cdot 17 + 1 = 256$, ($a = 17 - 1 = 16$) is an S-idempotent. As $256^2 \equiv 256 \pmod{272}$, $16^2 \equiv 256 \pmod{272}$ and $256 \cdot 16 \equiv 16 \pmod{272}$. Also $y = 17$, ($a = 15 \cdot 17 = 255$) is another S-idempotent. As $17^2 \equiv 17 \pmod{272}$, $255^2 \equiv 17 \pmod{272}$ and $17 \cdot 255 \equiv 255 \pmod{272}$.

We can generalize the above result as followings:

Theorem 2.6. *The ring $Z_{2^n p}$, p a prime > 2 has (at least) two S-idempotents for each of $\phi(2^n)$ types of prime p .*

Proof. Here p is one of the $\phi(2^n)$ form:

$$2^n m_1 + 1, \quad 2^n m_2 + 3, \quad \dots \quad 2^n m_{\phi(2^n)} + (2^n - 1).$$

We can find the two S-idempotents for each p as above. We are showing here for the prime $p = 2^n m_1 + 1$ only. If

$$p = 2^n m_1 + 1,$$

then

$$x = (2^n - 1)p + 1, \quad (a = p - 1)$$

and

$$y = p, \quad (a = (2^n - 1)p)$$

are S-idempotents.

Similarly we can find S-idempotents for each of the $\phi(2^n)$ form of prime p .

Theorem 2.7. *The ring Z_{3p} , p a prime > 3 has (at least) two S-idempotents of $\phi(3)$ types.*

Proof. Here p can be one of the form $3m + 1$ or $3m + 2$. We can apply the Theorem 2.6 for Z_{3p} also.

I. If $p = 3m + 1$, then $x = 2p + 1, (a = p - 1)$ and $y = p, (a = 2p)$ are S-idempotents.

II. If $p = 3m + 2$, then $x = p + 1, (a = 2p - 1)$ and $y = 2p, (a = p)$ are S-idempotents.

Example 2.7. In the ring $Z_{3 \cdot 5} = Z_{15} = \{0, 1, \dots, 14\}$, here $5 = 3 \cdot 1 + 2$. So $x = 5 + 1 = 6, (a = 2 \cdot 5 - 1 = 9)$ is an S-idempotent. As $6^2 \equiv 6(\text{mod}15), 9^2 \equiv 6(\text{mod}15)$ and $6 \cdot 9 \equiv 9(\text{mod}15)$. Also $y = 2 \cdot 5 = 10, (a = 5)$ is another S-idempotent. As $10^2 \equiv 10(\text{mod}15), 5^2 \equiv 10(\text{mod}15)$ and $10 \cdot 5 \equiv 5(\text{mod}15)$.

Remark: The above result is not true for the ring Z_{3^2p}, p prime > 3 . As, for $p = 9m + 5; x = 4p + 1, (a = 5p - 1)$ should be an S-idempotent from the above result. But we see it is not the case in general; for take the ring $Z_{3^2 \cdot 23} = Z_{207} = \{0, 1, \dots, 206\}$. Here $p = 9 \cdot 2 + 5$. Now take

$$x = 4 \cdot 23 + 1 = 93 \quad \text{and} \quad a = 5 \cdot 23 - 1 = 114.$$

But

$$x^2 \not\equiv x(\text{mod}207).$$

So x is not even an idempotent. So $x = 4p + 1$ is not an S-idempotent of Z_{3^2p} .

§3. S-idempotents in the group rings Z_2G

Here we prove the existence of Smarandache idempotents for the group rings Z_{3^2p} of the cyclic group G of order 2^np where p is a prime of the form $2^nt + 1$.

Example 3.2. Let $G = \{g/g^{52} = 1\}$ be the cyclic group of order $2^2 \cdot 13$. Consider the group ring Z_2G of the group G over Z_2 . Take

$$x = 1 + g^4 + g^8 + g^{12} + \dots + g^{44} + g^{48}$$

and

$$a = 1 + g^2 + g^4 + \dots + g^{22} + g^{24}$$

then

$$x^2 = x, \quad \text{and} \quad a^2 = x$$

also

$$x \cdot a = x.$$

So $x = 1 + g^4 + g^8 + g^{12} + \dots + g^{44} + g^{48}$ is a S-idempotent in Z_2G .

Theorem 3.1. Let Z_2G be the group ring of the finite cyclic group G of order 2^2p , where p is a prime of the form $2^2m + 1$, then the group ring Z_2G has non-trivial S-idempotents.

Proof. Here G is a cyclic group of order 2^2p , where p of the form $2^2m + 1$.

Take

$$x = 1 + g^4 + g^8 + \dots + g^{16m}$$

and

$$a = 1 + g^2 + g^4 + \dots + g^{8m}$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} x^2 &= (1 + g^4 + g^8 + \dots + g^{16m})^2 \\ &= 1 + g^4 + g^8 + \dots + g^{16m} \\ &= x. \end{aligned}$$

And

$$\begin{aligned} a^2 &= (1 + g^2 + g^4 + \dots + g^{8m})^2 \\ &= 1 + (g^2)^2 + (g^4)^2 + \dots + (g^{8m})^2 \\ &= x. \end{aligned}$$

Also

$$\begin{aligned} x \cdot a &= (1 + g^4 + g^8 + \dots + g^{16m})(1 + g^2 + g^4 + \dots + g^{8m}) \\ &= 1 + g^4 + g^8 + \dots + g^{16m} \\ &= x. \end{aligned}$$

So $x = 1 + g^4 + g^8 + \dots + g^{16m}$ is a S-idempotent in Z_2G .

Example 3.3. Let $G = \{g/g^{136} = 1\}$ be the cyclic group of order $2^3 \cdot 17$. Consider the group ring Z_2G of the group G over Z_2 .

Take

$$x = 1 + g^8 + g^{16} + \dots + g^{128}$$

and

$$a = 1 + g^4 + g^8 + \dots + g^{64}$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} x^2 &= (1 + g^8 + g^{16} + \dots + g^{128})^2 \\ &= 1 + g^8 + g^{16} + \dots + g^{128} \\ &= x. \end{aligned}$$

And

$$\begin{aligned} a^2 &= (1 + g^4 + g^8 + \dots + g^{64})^2 \\ &= 1 + (g^4)^2 + (g^8)^2 + \dots + (g^{64})^2 \\ &= x. \end{aligned}$$

Also

$$\begin{aligned} x \cdot a &= (1 + g^8 + g^{16} + \dots + g^{128})(1 + g^4 + g^8 + \dots + g^{64}) \\ &= 1 + g^8 + g^{64} + \dots + g^{128} \\ &= x. \end{aligned}$$

So $x = 1 + g^8 + g^{16} + \dots + g^{128}$ is a S-idempotent in Z_2G .

Theorem 3.2. *Let Z_2G be the group ring of a finite cyclic group G of order 2^3p , where p is a prime of the form $2^3m + 1$, then the group ring Z_2G has non-trivial S -idempotents.*

Proof. Here G is a cyclic group of order 2^3p , where p of the form $2^3m + 1$.

Take

$$x = 1 + g^8 + g^{16} + \dots + g^{8(p-1)}$$

and

$$a = 1 + g^4 + g^8 + \dots + g^{4(p-1)}$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} x^2 &= (1 + g^8 + g^{16} + \dots + g^{8(p-1)})^2 \\ &= 1 + g^8 + g^{16} + \dots + g^{8(p-1)} \\ &= x. \end{aligned}$$

And

$$\begin{aligned} a^2 &= (1 + g^4 + g^8 + \dots + g^{4(p-1)})^2 \\ &= 1 + (g^4)^2 + (g^8)^2 + \dots + (g^{4(p-1)})^2 \\ &= x. \end{aligned}$$

Also

$$\begin{aligned} x \cdot a &= (1 + g^8 + g^{16} + \dots + g^{8(p-1)})(1 + g^4 + g^8 + \dots + g^{4(p-1)}) \\ &= 1 + g^8 + g^{16} + \dots + g^{8(p-1)} \\ &= x. \end{aligned}$$

So $x = 1 + g^8 + g^{16} + \dots + g^{8(p-1)}$ is a S -idempotent in Z_2G .

We can generalize the above two results as followings:

Theorem 3.3. *Let Z_2G be the group ring of a finite cyclic group G of order 2^np , where p is a prime of the form $2^nt + 1$, then the group ring Z_2G has non-trivial S -idempotents.*

Proof. Here G is a cyclic group of order 2^np , where p of the form $2^nt + 1$.

Take

$$x = 1 + g^{2^n} + g^{2^{n \cdot 2}} + \dots + g^{2^n(p-1)}$$

and

$$a = 1 + g^{2^{n-1}} + g^{2^{n-1} \cdot 2} + \dots + g^{2^{n-1} \cdot (p-1)}$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} x^2 &= (1 + g^{2^n} + g^{2^{n \cdot 2}} + \dots + g^{2^n(p-1)})^2 \\ &= 1 + g^{2^n} + g^{2^{n \cdot 2}} + \dots + g^{2^n(p-1)} \\ &= x. \end{aligned}$$

And

$$\begin{aligned} a^2 &= (1 + g^{2^{n-1}} + g^{2^{n-1} \cdot 2} + \dots + g^{2^{n-1} \cdot (p-1)})^2 \\ &= 1 + (g^{2^{n-1}})^2 + (g^{2^{n-1} \cdot 2})^2 + \dots + (g^{2^{n-1} \cdot (p-1)})^2 \\ &= x. \end{aligned}$$

Also

$$\begin{aligned} x \cdot a &= (1 + g^{2^n} + g^{2^n \cdot 2} + \dots + g^{2^n(p-1)})(1 + g^{2^{n-1}} + g^{2^{n-1} \cdot 2} + \dots + g^{2^{n-1} \cdot (p-1)}) \\ &= 1 + g^{2^n} + g^{2^n \cdot 2} + \dots + g^{2^n(p-1)} \\ &= x. \end{aligned}$$

So $x = 1 + g^{2^n} + g^{2^n \cdot 2} + \dots + g^{2^n(p-1)}$ is a S-idempotent in Z_2G .

Corollary 3.1. *Let Z_2S_n be the group ring of a symmetric group S_n where $n = 2^n p$, and p is a prime of the form $2^nt + 1$, then the group ring Z_2S_n has non-trivial S-idempotents.*

Proof. Here Z_2S_n is a group ring where $n = 2^n p$, and p of the form $2^nt + 1$. Clearly Z_2S_n contains a finite cyclic group of order $2^n p$. Then by the Theorem 3.3, Z_2S_n has a non-trivial S-idempotent.

§4. Conclusions

Here we have mainly proved the existence of S-idempotents in certain types of group rings. But it is interesting to enumerate the number of S-idempotents for the group rings Z_2G and Z_2S_n in the Theorem 3.3 and Corollary 3.1. We feel that Z_2G can have only one S-idempotent but we are not in a position to give a proof for it. Also, the problem of finding S-idempotents in Z_pS_n (and Z_pG) where $(p, n) = 1$ (and $(p, |G|) = 1$) or $(p, n) = d \neq 1$ (and $(p, |G|) = d \neq 1$) are still interesting number theoretic problems.

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